

Mechanical performance, residual stress and microstructural analysis of multiple ceramic matrix composite systems

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Outline

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Introduction

- Ceramic matrix composites (CMCs) offer:
 - Superior toughness than monolithic ceramics
 - Lower specific densities than current metals/alloys
 - Better high-temperature performance retention.

→ Suitable for use in gas turbines.
- Classification:
 - Non-oxide (e.g. silicon carbide – SiC)
 - Oxide (e.g. alumina – Al₂O₃).

Introduction

- Non-oxide SiC CMCs:
 - + Excellent high temperature strength
 - + Low density and CTE
 - Intermediate temperature (500 – 800°C) oxidation and environmental embrittlement.

- Oxide (Al₂O₃-based) CMCs:
 - + Improved oxidation stability over SiC CMCs → better lifetimes
 - Reduced mechanical performance: strength and creep.

Introduction

- Although a crack deflection mechanism is described in the literature, there appears to be little understanding of crack nucleation, propagation and deflection, especially in the case of porous matrix oxide CMC.

→ Aim of the present study: establishing the link between microstructure, distribution of residual stresses, the damage mechanism and the failure mode of the CMCs under room and extreme conditions that are relevant for the service environments of the materials.

Experimental Procedure: Materials

- Four oxide CMC systems tested (fibre/matrix):
 - Woven Nextel™ 312/SiOC (312/SiOC)
 - Woven Nextel™ 720/Aluminosilicate (720/AS)
 - Woven Nextel™ 720/Alumina (720/A) – GenI and GenIII:
 - GenIII samples present increased fibre tow thickness compared to GenI.

Experimental Procedure: Methods

- Microstructural analyses:
 - Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM): ACCIS, UK
 - Absorption Synchrotron X-Ray Computed Microtomography (DLS A- μ XCT): DLS, UK
- Residual stress measurements:
 - Micro-Raman spectroscopy (Bristol Physics, UK)
 - Stressed peak shows a linear shift from non-stressed peak. [1]

$$\Delta\omega = \sigma_R * C$$

where $\Delta\omega$ is the wavenumber shift, σ_R is the residual stress and C is the Raman coefficient.

Experimental Procedure: Methods

- Mechanical testing and damage observation:
 - 4-point bending (4-PB) with *in situ* Digital Image Correlation (DIC): ACCIS.
 - Dimensions vary according to supplied specimens.
 - High temperature 3-point bending (3-PB) with *in situ* absorption μ XCT (ALS A- μ XCT): ALS, USA (in collaboration with Prof. Robert Ritchie).
 - Fixed dimensions: 3x3x25mm (21 mm support span).
- Post-processing:
 - Avizo Digital Volume Correlation (DVC): Bristol Physics, UK.

Results: 312/SiOC

- Mean 4-PB flexural strength: 148.0 ± 22.0 MPa
- Relatively brittle behaviour
- Strengthening after initial load drop is observable in certain cases
- Load drops are primarily associated with delamination.

4-PB Load vs. Crosshead displacement for 312/SiOC samples.

Results: 312/SiOC

SEM of as-processed 312/SiOC.

SEM of fractured 312/SiOC.

- Fibre pull-out clearly visible: decreasing with increasing depth.
- Possible formation of a SiO_2 glassy layer \rightarrow embrittlement.

Results and Discussion: 720/AS

0 2000 [μm]

DLS A-μXCT of as-processed 720/AS.

- ‘Tow splitting’ can be observed
 - In certain areas, so-called ‘three-way splits’ may occur.
 - Very large defects can be observed in areas of tow splitting.

Results: 720/AS

- Mean flexural strength:
181.5 ± 27.0 MPa;
- Multiple strengthening steps observed in both cases.
- Marked difference in failure load – consequence of local macroporosity.
 - Sample 1 showed only delamination
 - Sample 2 showed delamination and buckling.

4-PB Load vs. Crosshead displacement for 720/AS samples.

Results: 720/AS

- 720/AS Sample 1 – Delamination cracks

DIC image of 720/AS Sample 1 after first (top) and after second (bottom) load drop.

Results: 720/AS

- 720/AS Sample 2 – Fibre buckling.

DIC image of 720/AS Sample 2 after third load drop.

Results: 720/A – GenI

DLS A- μ XCT of as-processed 720/A - GenI.

- Thickness of fibre tows appears to be smaller compared to 720/AS
- Tow splitting is still present , albeit giving rise to smaller fibre curvatures
- Longitudinal cracks can be observed at the top and bottom side of the specimen
- Less observable macropores than 720/AS.

Results: 720/A – GenI

- RT 4-PB Flexural strength: 230.7 MPa.
- Strengthening is observable.
- Strength is higher than both 720/AS.

4-PB Load vs. Crosshead displacement for 720/A sample.

Results: 720/A – GenI

3-PB Flexural strength:

- **RT:** 239.5 MPa (214.8 MPa before first load drop);
- **1100°C:** 156.8 MPa.
- Main failure mechanism: delamination.
- Fibre pull-out not observed.

3-PB Load vs. Crosshead displacement for 720/A GenI

Results: 720/A – GenIII

0 2000 [μm]

ALS A-μXCT of as-processed 720/A - GenIII.

- GenIII samples show increased fibre tow thickness compared to GenI;
- Tow splitting is still very much present;
- The apparition and the density of shrinkage cracks is another unique characteristic of GenIII samples.

Results: 720/A – GenIII

3-PB Flexural strength:

- **RT:** 93.5 MPa;
- **1100°C:** 129.0 MPa;
- **900°C:** 84.6 MPa.
- Main failure mechanism: delamination.
- Fibre pull-out not observed.

3-PB Load vs. Crosshead displacement for 720/A GenI

Results and Discussion: 720/A – DVC

-0.022 -0.00625 0.0095
E_{zz}

0 2000 [μm]

E_{zz} strain mapping superimposed on a 1100°C 720/A GenIII specimen

- DVC allows the 3D mapping of strain;
- Two different approaches can be used:
 - Local: no displacement continuity at the boundaries between subsets
 - Global: continuity between subsets.
- Present case (imported with $1vx = 1\mu m$):
 - Local volume: 90 μm ;
 - Global volume: 65 μm .

Results: Residual Stress

- On 720/AS correlation between mapping area and R1 peak shift position was obtained.

Raman mapping area

R1 peak shift mapping of Cr³⁺ impurity ubiquitous in alumina containing compounds (720/AS).

Conclusions

- Presently, the results indicate a strong dependence of the mechanical performance on the microstructure of the tested systems.
- The microstructure, however, appears to be heavily inconsistent even throughout specimens of the same batch
 - High degree of variability within the mechanical performance of the systems.
- The loss of load bearing capacity occurs almost exclusively through delamination as opposed to load induced through-thickness cracks.

Conclusions

- The differences between the flexural strengths at varying temperatures are still under investigation and it is believed that DVC will be a powerful tool in this regard
- Raman experiments yielded a peak shift map which shows good correlation to the mapping area. However, the calculation of residual stress from the wavenumber proved to be problematic due to the inaccurate calibration of the instrument.

Future Work

- Continuation of DVC analyses on GenIII samples;
- Further μ XCT scans under more complex environments (e.g. high temperature + steam) and pre-treatments (long-term high temperature exposure);
- Re-evaluation of Micro-Raman spectroscopy to improve accuracy through better instrument calibration;
- Investigation of other potential methods to measure residual stress in order to establish their influence on performance of the CMCs.

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